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SOCIAL REPRESENTATIONS OF THE MEDIA ABOUT CRIME IN THE TOURIST REGION OF PUERTO VALLARTA, MEXICO

Abstract. Violence and crime are among the most impactful topics in global media, shaping narratives, collective imaginations, and perceptions of places worldwide. In tourism, perceptions of (in)security play a decisive role in motivating or deterring visits to a destination. Mexico presents a paradigmatic case for analyzing this dynamic, as it remains a top global tourism destination despite its reputation for insecurity—evidenced, for instance, by U.S. government travel advisories warning against visiting certain regions. Focusing on Puerto Vallarta and Bahía de Banderas, this study examines how print and digital media construct social representations of violence and crime in a tourist context. Using a sample of 97 news reports (from a total of 622) published by *Noticieros* (affiliated with Televisa) between 2015 and 2020, we employed Iramuteq software for lexical analysis, identifying three thematic clusters: 1) Crimes in the region: Reports emphasizing "spectacular" crimes (e.g., shootouts) that deviate from everyday life; 2) Crimes involving public figures: Coverage of high-profile individuals as victims or perpetrators; 3) Criminal organizations: Focus on cartels and globally notorious figures (e.g., the "El Chapo" family). Findings reveal a discrepancy between media portrayals and local crime statistics, where the media selectively represents violence – prioritizing sensational or celebrity-linked events while omitting or euphemizing everyday criminality. This framing constructs a partial reality that anchors public perceptions of crime but fails to reflect the lived insecurity of residents. Crucially, this mediated representation minimizes the perceived risks for tourists, thereby avoiding significant negative impacts on tourism flows and economic revenue. The study concludes that media representations of crime in Puerto Vallarta promotes a generic, diffuse notion of insecurity, which benefits the tourism industry by maintaining an attractive image despite underlying safety concerns. This raises critical questions about the ethical responsibilities of media in shaping tourist perceptions and the socioeconomic trade-offs between accurate reporting and destination branding.

Keywords: Social representations, Media, Tourism, Crime, Puerto Vallarta

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СОЦИАЛЬНЫЕ ПРЕДСТАВЛЕНИЯ В СМИ О ПРЕСТУПНОСТИ В ТУРИСТИЧЕСКОМ РЕГИОНЕ ПУЭРТО-ВАЛЬЯРТА (МЕКСИКА)

Насилие и преступность – явления, оказывающие мощное влияние на глобальную аудиторию телевидения и на туристическую индустрию. Средства массовой информации активно формируют образы и конструируют представления о различных уголках мира в глобальном контексте. В сфере туризма восприятие безопасности пункта назначения играет ключевую роль, определяя желание или нежелание путешественников посетить тот или иной город или регион. Мексика представляет собой яркий пример для анализа взаимосвязи насилия и преступности с туристической индустрией. Несмотря на свою популярность и значительный поток туристов, страна часто ассоциируется с высокой криминальностью, что подтверждается, например, предупреждениями правительства США своим гражданам о необходимости воздержаться от посещения определённых регионов. В этом контексте авторы статьи рассматривают на примере туристического города Пуэрто-Вальярта и залива Бандерас проблему того, как представления о проблемах преступности отражаются в печатных/цифровых СМИ. В качестве объекта анализа взяты новостные программы сети Televisa за последние 5 лет (с янв. 2015 г. по дек. 2020 г.), благодаря чему удалось получить выборку, насчитывающую 97 репортаж из общего числа 622 опубликованных репортажей за указанный период. Данные были проанализированы с использованием программного обеспечения Iramuteq, в результате чего в аналитическом корпусе выделено три кластера: 1) преступления в регионе, объединивший репортажи, целью которых было сообщить о преступлениях, произошедших в регионе Пуэрто-Вальярта, и имевших определённое значение из-за их «зрелищной» природы, например, перестрелки; кластеры 2) преступления с участием публичных фигур и 3) криминальные организации – объединили репортажи, охватывающие преступления, совершенные в отношении или публичными фигурами, или картелями и другими криминальными организациями соответственно. Анализ результатов указывает на то, что местная реальность с проблемой преступности частично объективно не отражается национальными СМИ. Эти проблемы находят своё отражение в СМИ только тогда, когда они обладают способностью привлечь внимание читателей. Изученный пример социальных представлений в СМИ о преступности в регионе Пуэрто-Вальярта позволяет глубже понять, как медийные образы влияют на восприятие безопасности и туристический поток.

Ключевые слова: социальные представления; СМИ, туризм, преступность, Пуэрто-Вальярта

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1. Introduction

The phenomenon of violence and crime stands as one of the main topics with the highest global television audience impact. As a situation experienced and directly affecting life in society, the media tends to amplify reports that highlight these [sensational/unusual] aspects of everyday life, as such topics often lead to an exponential increase in viewership.

On the other hand, by giving visibility to such situations, the media, much like universities, end up becoming important mechanisms that play fundamental roles in the development of policies, mainly related to public security. After all, the media, particularly television, due to its extensive national reach, enables the construction of common sense and the discussion of such issues within the social sphere.

In this context, given its power, the media contributes to the construction of narratives and perceptions about various places in a global context. By creating these representations of places, it attracts the attention of numerous individuals on both a national and international scale. Therefore, the importance that the media assigns to a particular news item can alter the local, regional, or international dynamics, influencing the economy, livelihoods, among other aspects. Likewise, it wouldn't be any different in the tourism sector, where the visibility provided by media outlets directly impacts the influx of tourists to these destinations.

When it comes to tourism, the media has been portraying the paradisiacal regions of Latin America, including Mexico, as one of the main tourist destinations today. Regarding Mexico, the city of Puerto Vallarta is famous for its beaches and various opportunities for water sports. As tourism is the primary economic activity, media outlets tend to attribute positive characteristics to the area, such as its nightlife and natural beauty, while overlooking other social aspects, such as crime.

Therefore, this article aims to analyze how social representations of crime are constructed in Puerto Vallarta, Mexico, and

whether these representations end up influencing the region's tourism development. To achieve this, *Noticieros*, linked to the Televisa media network, is taken as the object of analysis.

Crime and Violence

From a historical perspective, it's noteworthy how sociology and criminology have dedicated their research to understanding the phenomenon of criminality and the causal factors leading individuals to commit a specific crime. Various approaches have sought to elucidate this characteristic. Broadly speaking, the Classical School conceives the individual as responsible for their actions, suggesting that criminal behavior is purely and simply the result of the individual's will. Within this framework, punishments are intended to re-educate the individual for life in society, where the type of punishment is related to the severity of the crime, enabling the offender to learn from their actions (Baratta, 2007). On the other hand, the positivist school believes that individuals don't have the choice of not being a criminal; this deterministic perspective holds that criminals possess biological characteristics that define them as such. Thus, the aim is not to rehabilitate the criminal but to respond to delinquent behavior with a penalty that has an impact, essentially repaying evil with evil (Baratta, 2007).

From this perspective, one of the most well-known works in this field was developed by psychiatrist Cesare Lombroso (1835 – 1909), who attributed the cause of criminality to the occurrence of individual pathologies in human beings (Baratta, 2007). In a subsequent study, Durkheim (2002) theorized that criminality is much more related to moral deviation than other factors. He adds that the individual, regardless of their beliefs, "must respect the life, property, and honor of my peers, even if they are not your relatives or compatriots". The sociologist further states that "the most immoral act par excellence is murder and robbery, and the immorality of these acts doesn't diminish at all when committed against foreigners" (Durkheim, 2002, p. 153).

At the turn of the 20th century, various studies in different fields of knowledge brought new interpretations to criminality. One of the most important institutions dedicated to this phenomenon was the Chicago School. Researchers from various branches of science such as economics, sociology, anthropology, etc., pointed out characteristics like socio-spatial distribution, economic, environmental, and health conditions as determinants for crime.

Within this context, various theoretical currents emerged to comprehend the phenomenon of criminality, among which is the Labeling Approach. Understood as the Theory of labeling, reaction symbols, symbolic interactionism, the Labeling Approach, developed in the 1960s, had its main exponents as Howard Becker, Erving Goffman, Mead, and Lemert (Sapori & Soares, 2015; Viana, 2016). According to this theoretical perspective, the labeling that a particular group or individuals attach to an individual influences or drives them toward involvement in the world of crime. This stigmatization carried out by people or groups with different social values can influence and magnify the actions of an individual (criminal) (Sapori & Soares, 2015).

One of the works that gained prominence in the 20th century and brought a new interpretation to criminality was Howard S. Becker's book "Outsiders: Studies in the Sociology of Deviance" (2009). In the work, the author emphasizes that he never considered his work as a new approach but rather as part of the craft of a good sociologist.

Throughout the book, Becker (2002) replaces the term "crime" with what he calls "deviance." For him, the term deviance focuses on broader issues than just those related to the practice of criminal acts themselves. Thus, various activities are characterized as deviant, but not all are actually crimes. They are usually linked to collective actions, where a particular group determines whether certain behaviors are right or wrong according to their own rules. Those behaviors that receive disapproval are discouraged from being practiced.

As Becker (2002) points out, within a particular society, there are various groups that subdivide according to their interests (religious groups, sports groups, mafia and cartel groups, criminal groups, etc.). All these groups are subject to a general rule (the community rule in which they are embedded), and they all create their own norms for their members, which can also be violated by their members.

Several authors, including Becker and Goffman, have used the term "deviance" in their studies, but it's worth noting that this nomenclature doesn't solely relate to crime; there are several other possibilities within this concept that go far beyond criminal acts. The violation of a simple social rule, not codified in a legal system, constitutes deviance.

Becker (2002) used the term "outsiders" to designate those who break rules, whether legal or not. These individuals often don't conform to a particular social group and end up being labeled by the group or part of society. Furthermore, according to Becker (2002), there's an ambiguous conception regarding those who create rules and those who break them, where rule-breakers also perceive those who establish/create social norms as outsiders since these social rules conflict with or go against their personal desires.

Another significant contribution to the field of sociology of crime was the concept of stigma developed by Goffman (1982). According to the author, this term originated from the Greeks and referred to something different in those who bore bodily marks. Typically, those who carried these marks were slaves, criminals, fugitives – individuals who were supposed to be kept away from social contact and interaction, restricted from public places. In the Christian era, these signs denoted something positive; that is, a person bearing marks on the skin was considered blessed by divine grace.

Goffman (1982), in studying the concept of stigma, ended up popularizing the term and bringing its applications to the current context. According to the author, "currently, the term is widely used somewhat similarly to its original literal sense, but it is more applied to

the disgrace itself than to its bodily evidence" (Goffman, 1982, p. 5). Thus, in the author's conception, stigma refers to the attribution of phenotypic and/or cultural characteristics used as markers to differentiate and discredit individuals who possess such undesirable stereotypes.

Following Baratta's line of thought (2007), there's the accusatory naturalization of certain societal groups, associating them with a criminal life or a propensity for criminality. The author further contemplates that these actions lead the individual to begin to see themselves as part of this accusatory whole. In other words, due to these bombardments of social stereotypes, the individual starts believing that crime is the only way left for them to express themselves in the world, contributing to the awakening of delinquency.

Beginning of the form

Stigmas possess a value-laden power where their externalization or dissemination can influence behaviors and opinions. Hence, ascribing adjectives to a social group, in this case, as prone to crime, leads an entire society to mistakenly perceive them as criminals. Baratta (2007) suggests that this attribution of stigmas or physical characteristics to what could potentially be a criminal leads to criminality becoming part of the reality where stigmatized individuals are placed. Consequently, criminal infractions become normalized in that context due to the presence of these individuals, contributing to those with such characteristics being increasingly depicted as delinquents. Therefore, this labeling of individuals tends to reinforce not only fear but also the delinquent identity, even if it is not factually based.

Moreover, individuals whose characteristics differ from the delinquent profile, even if they have committed illicit and criminal acts, tend to receive milder sanctions or less rigorous penalties, contrasting with the relationship between punishment and the committed offense (Baratta, 2007). Hence, despite society being guided by conduct rules, representations about the individual and/or criminal act will structure themselves based on the

stigma of the criminal profile. Thus, different penalties may be applied to offenders for the same offense based on the status they carry. This observation echoes Goffman's (1982) considerations wherein the author points out that:

Social environments establish categories of people likely to be found within them. The routines of social interaction in established environments allow us to engage with "other people" expectedly without particular attention or reflection. Therefore, when a stranger is presented to us, the initial aspects enable us to anticipate their category and their attributes, their "social identity" – to use a better term than "social status," as it includes attributes like "honesty" as well as structural attributes like "occupation" (Goffman, p. 5, 1982).

Criminality and violence, in a global context, involve various types of social actors, institutions, and organizations, such as the mafia. Crimes like drug and arms trafficking, homicides, theft, robbery, kidnapping, are among the most prevalent worldwide and often establish an interconnected relationship.

Drug trafficking and homicide are significantly linked, as a considerable portion of traffickers is brutally murdered due to constant territory disputes and debts. The same holds for theft and robbery, where a substantial number of drug users engage in these acts to sustain their addictions. Moreover, drug consumption has, in recent years, fostered an illicit international trade.

Many of these crimes are financed by criminal organizations such as gangs, the mafia, and cartels. They involve a high number of individuals who coordinate with the same purpose and often involve governmental bodies and entities, as evidenced by (Tranfaglia, 2010):

The relationship between the mafia and politics – it is worth emphasizing based on consolidated results from Italian and international scientific research – is structural and not accidental; the businesses cover a very broad spectrum

concerning public tenders in all sectors, arms and drug trafficking, to which must be added human trafficking and organ trafficking (of which neither the dimensions nor all judicial evidence are yet known) (Tranfaglia, 2010, p. 118).

In many cases, due to political convenience, violent crimes, particularly those associated with organized crime, are not adequately reported to the population by the media. This situation was noted by Tranfaglia (2010) in his study on mafia-politics in Italy.

Tranfaglia's (2010) research sheds light on the involvement of various public figures (senators, prime ministers, governors) with the mafia, resulting in thousands of pages of legal proceedings throughout history, detailing what was omitted by the media. Therefore, many drug seizures and arrests of local trafficking leaders may not accurately reflect the reality of drug trafficking, as the 'masterminds' behind these actions remain at large (Cunha, 2019) and consequently are not part of public safety statistics.

Furthermore, according to Cunha (2019), actions that go against the norms of civility are morally and socially condemned. Although not criminal, these actions are perceived by society as deviant, which, in turn, can lead people to regard a particular location as unsafe if these 'uncivil' individuals are present. Additionally, the author points out a correlation between gender and the feeling of insecurity, where the female population tends to feel less secure due to a socio-historical construction that has solidified certain types of behaviors, leading women to adopt reclusive behaviors, avoiding certain places, going out at night, among others.

For Cunha (2019), the perception of insecurity is linked to fear, which in turn is anchored in a series of objective and subjective factors (stigma, stereotypes, among others). These subjective factors, to a certain extent, delineate the sense of insecurity, the increase or decrease in criminality, but not only that; they are also part of a representation system and can sometimes contribute to the stigmatization of individuals.

2. Social Representations Theory and the Media

Created by Emile Durkheim (1858 - 1917) in the form of the Theory of Collective Representations and subsequently reworked by the social psychologist Serge Moscovici (1928 - 2014) as the Theory of Social Representations (TRS), TRS has evolved into an interdisciplinary theory, encompassing various fields of knowledge such as psychology, anthropology, sociology, administration, among others.

According to Moscovici (2015), even before the creation of the Theory of Social Representations, these representations already circulated within society but did not carry their theoretical importance. It fell upon social psychology to understand the more detailed elements that engendered these representations. Hence, Piaget was responsible for initiating these studies by researching representations in the world of children, making him one of the pioneers in applying the theory and one of the primary examples even to this day.

Just as its interdisciplinary nature, its concepts diversify according to its field of application. In this sense, Minayo (2020) adds:

Social Representations is a philosophical term that signifies the reproduction of a perception retained in memory or the content of thought. In the Social Sciences, they are defined as thought categories that express reality, explaining it, justifying it, or questioning it (Minayo, 2020: 73).

According to Moscovici (1978) and Jodelet (2001), daily life in society is surrounded by social representations, which are present in various forms of social manifestations, whether in speeches, symbols, images, and virtually in all forms of communication. Jodelet (2001) emphasizes the importance of social representations in the communicational process that permeates social relations. For the author, "with social representations, we deal with phenomena directly observable or reconstructed through scientific work" (Jodelet, 2001, p. 1).

For the consolidation of social representations, two processes are fundamental in this

context: anchoring and objectification. Anchoring, according to Moscovici (2015), is a phenomenon that aims to make something unfamiliar to a particular individual become familiar. In this case, the experiences and sociocultural aspects of a specific social group will be the basis that provides the elements for anchoring to occur. On the other hand, objectification is an attempt to bring something abstract/from the mental plane to the concrete/material plane. Moscovici (2015) adds that objectification 'combines the idea of unfamiliarity with that of reality, becoming the true essence of reality' (Moscovici, 2015, p. 71).

Another fundamental element for the construction, anchoring, and objectification of social representations is the mass media. Through these, social representations begin to circulate freely among viewers. After all, the news reports, the photographs:

[...] that illustrate the captions of the photos, the very structure of the news stories disseminated by the press, while contributing to the formation or transformation of the public's worldview, reflect the interests and aspirations of specific social groups (Bueno, 2002, p. 101).

Given this, highlighting the power of media, Hall (2013) argues that through the dissemination of images and sounds, media construct a regime of representation. This regime emerges from the diverse meanings converging through the intertextual reading of news considering its socio-historical aspects.

Furthermore, as the "uncommon" tends to captivate viewers and attract audiences, media outlets tend to concentrate their efforts on broadcasting "eccentric" occurrences in daily life (Cogo, 2012). Consequently, crime, perceived as an "event," facilitates the construction of narratives and stories, invoking issues of social, cultural, and economic significance woven into the social fabric.

Therefore, comprehending the power and importance of media in shaping social representations, it becomes essential to study how regional media creates a representational regime concerning crime.

3. Methodology

This is a qualitative-quantitative, documentary, and exploratory research aimed at analyzing written materials (texts, newspapers, among others) as well as non-written materials (videos, audios, among others (Lakatos & Marconi, 2001). Therefore, the empirical universe, the second stage of the research, consists of the virtual environment on the televisa.com website, associated with the Mexican media conglomerate, Televisa.

Televisa was founded in the 1970s through the merger of Television Independiente de México and Telesistema Mexicano, becoming one of the largest commercial television networks globally. It stands as the largest in Mexico and is the largest producer of Spanish-language media content, exporting its productions to various countries (Televisa, 2021).

The analyzed material consists of news reports available on the noticiero website, affiliated with Televisa, providing news about various cities in Mexico. The choice of this website was due to its affiliation with the Televisa group and the large audience it holds in the country. It also presents reports in a media format used to broadcast news from cities daily, specifically in the case of this study, Puerto Vallarta.

The final sample related to the news comprised a total of 97 televised reports within the period from January 2015 to December 2020. Once the reports were obtained, the material was transcribed and analyzed. Initially, the report headlines were tabulated and analyzed using the Interface de R pour analyses Multidimensionnelles de Textes et de Questionnaires (Iramuteq) software, version 0.7 Alpha2, 2020. This software enables quantitative lexical analysis. In this type of analysis, words are considered a textual unit, taking into account their contextualization in the textual corpus. Subsequently, the contents of the reports were analyzed (Bardin, 2001), considering the narratives of the reporters, interviewees, and transmitted images.

4. Results and Discussion

A total of 97 reports covering crime in

Puerto Vallarta were found. The year with the highest number was 2019 with 27 reports, followed by 2020 with 24, 2018 with 23, 2016 with 10, 2015 with 7, and 2017 with 6.

Analyzing the report titles with the assistance of Iramuteq 0.7 Alpha2 version 2020 software, a corpus of 101 text segments (TS) was found, utilizing 110 TS (85.27%). There were 1061 occurrences (words, forms, or terms), comprising 416 different words, with

286 appearing only once, and an average frequency of occurrence of 26.96% and 68.75% per TS.

Through Descending Hierarchical Classification (CHD), three distinct classes of text segments were generated. CHD takes into account the distribution of words in the text segments. The classes were categorized as: Crimes in the region (1), Crimes involving public figures (2), and Criminal organizations (3) (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 – Dendrogram of the descending hierarchical classification of report titles¹

Through the dendrogram, we have three classes. Initially, there's a division into two sub-corpora, with Class 1 on the left and Classes 2 and 3 on the right, further subdividing. Exploring the dendrogram reveals that Class 1 (Crimes in the region) groups reports aiming to cover crimes that occurred in the Puerto Vallarta region, possessing a certain media relevance due to their 'spectacular' nature (Cogo, 2012), such as the local population's perception of public safety but lacking national commotion, for instance:

Class 1 – Spring breakers llegan a Puerto Vallarta (2015);

Class 1 – Mujeres perciben mayor inseguridad que hombres, según el INEGI (2017);

Class 1 – Matan a presunto ladrón en camión de pasajeros en la CDMX (2018). Balacera en bar de Puerto Vallarta deja una mujer muerta (2020).

Classes 2 and 3 (Crimes involving public figures, Criminal organizations) group reports

that cover crimes committed against or by public figures and carried out by cartels and other criminal organizations, respectively. The crimes grouped in these two classes are those that gained national attention, such as:

Class 2 – 'El Pantera 16,' regional leader of the Gulf Cartel, was a police officer in Tamaulipas (2018);

Class 2 – Detienen a jefe del Cártel del Golfo en Puerto Vallarta (2018). Class 2 - Captan momento en que integrantes del CJNG interceptan a jóvenes en Puerto Vallarta (2020);

Class 3 – Vinculan a proceso a Xóchitl Tress, exfuncionaria del gobierno de Javier Duarte Lavado_de_dinero (2019);

Class 3 – Secuestro del hijo de 'El Chapo' Guzmán y cinco personas más en Puerto Vallarta (2016);

Class 3 – Investigan asesinato de Aristóteles Sandoval (2020).

In terms of the main crimes reported in the news, it is evident that they revolved

¹ Source: Authors' elaboration (2021)

around murders/homicides, kidnappings, drug trafficking, and robbery. It's noteworthy that only one report covered an environmental crime, specifically an attempted theft of a turtle, which aired in August 2018.

It's important to note that while there were reports addressing the population's sense of insecurity, particularly the fear experienced by women in Puerto Vallarta, no news was found addressing violence against women in its various forms (rape, domestic violence, among others). However, contrary to the televised reports, data from INEGI (2020) indicates that over 80% of women in the Puerto Vallarta region feel insecure when walking the city streets, and more than 20% of the total population believe that the insecurity situation is likely to worsen in the coming years. According to Becker (2002), referencing a study by Davis, there exists a distortion between reported crimes and actual occurrences. Consequently, the media coverage of criminal acts in newspapers, for instance, influences people's perception of an increase or decrease in crime.

Having said that, it was observed that the media coverage of local crimes (Class 1), such as robbery, theft, murder, and kidnapping, among others, only occurs when they possess sensational elements suitable for exploitation, such as the kidnapping of an influential businessman, a jewelry store robbery, or a shootout in a bar. In these reports, sensationalization begins with the release of security camera footage; the criminals, for the most part, conform to the stereotype of the prison population, who are mostly low-income and from peripheral areas. This portrayal of crime, as discussed by Durkheim (2002) in the context of the Italian school, relates to an unfounded conception where phenotypic/pathological characteristics dictate a predisposition to crime.

There is a dehumanization of criminals; they are referred to as monsters, for example, contributing to the stigmatization/stereotyping of peripheral populations as potential criminals/monsters. Even though there may be security camera footage, it does not clearly

capture the physiognomy of the offenders. Consequently, the way the media addresses them in reports allows for the construction of an imagery representation of culpability, even in cases where there has been no confrontation/criminal investigation.

Presenting itself as the antithesis of the profile of criminals from Class 1, in Class 2, some reports highlighted a case involving a Mexican actor accused of pedophilia. The news is presented with an air of astonishment, after all, it concerns a white, good-looking, and successful man. Thus, as the media has the power to influence the population's perception of crime, by representing this figure that differs from the stereotyped profile of the criminal, it contributes to redefining representations. However, the way the news is addressed does not enhance the image of a successful individual as a potential criminal, as is done with low-income and/or peripheral populations. This highlights that despite Lombroso's postulations having been refuted long ago, to some extent, there is a maintenance of criminal stereotypes through the media.

In a report linked to Class 1, it was televised in October 2015 that a group of young people was detained with 50 grams of marijuana. This group of young people was portrayed as users; however, as Cunha (2019) aptly points out, a media narrative was structured in which the use of illicit substances made individuals susceptible to committing various criminal acts against private property, such as robbery, theft, among others, creating not only the stigmatization of the drug addict but of drugs as a whole.

Nevertheless, regarding the small number of news items in Class 1 (a total of 17), that is, news presenting regional crime, it is inferred that, being a national media outlet, cases of local crimes, which could interfere with the economy given that Puerto Vallarta is a tourist region, are not covered by the mainstream media. Such observations align with analyses conducted by the Bank of Mexico (2019), where results indicate that the demand for tourist locations in the country is directly related to the perception tourists have

about local security. In this study, analyzing Google trends from 2008 to 2018, it is noted that there was an increase in tourism demand in Puerto Vallarta, for example, as tourists do not perceive the destination as unsafe.

In view of this, it can be said that the absence of the dissemination of this news can be understood as a strategy that disrupts the circulation of representations; after all, for the consolidation of a representation, communication is essential (Moscovici, 2015; Jodelet, 2001). In the absence thereof, there is no mental stimulus for formation by the public—foreign tourists, nationals, and the Mexican population not residing in the region of Puerto Vallarta—and thus, representations of insecurity do not consolidate.

On the other hand, the reports in Classes 2 and 3, as they do not concern crimes against 'common' individuals, show a large number, totaling 81. This significant number, especially when compared to Class 1, is not only because they involve public figures but also because they are somehow detached from everyday life. In Class 2, as mentioned earlier, there are reports portraying political crimes, crimes committed by TV celebrities, crimes against politicians, etc. Two specific crimes were incessantly covered—the assassination of Aristoteles Sandoval and the arrest of the soap opera actor accused of pedophilia.

The reports that covered the assassination of the former governor of Jalisco, Aristoteles Sandoval, include footage of the shooting, detailed information about the area where the attack took place with diagrams and maps, and images of the 'Distrito/5' restaurant where the incident occurred.

The arrangement of videos and images invokes emotional perception more intensely than the discourse, contributing to the structuring of representation in the popular imagination (Hall, 2016; Menasche, 2005). This can be observed in the reports about the assassination of Aristoteles, where even those not primarily focused on the murder but rather on the investigation replayed footage of the shooting and the restaurant during their broadcast. These same images were repeated

several times in news reports and on different months within the same broadcasting channel.

Henceforth, as a strategy to provoke public emotion, apart from the images, in all reports that addressed the subject, phrases such as 'When the former governor got up to go to the bathroom, he was brutally attacked by an armed individual who shot him in the back' were stated by journalists and news anchors. Furthermore, in all reports, a brief background about the victim was presented similar to the following:

Aristoteles Sandoval was born in Guadalajara in 1974 and served as mayor of Guadalajara between 2010 and 2012 and as governor of Jalisco between 2013 and 2018 for the Institutional Revolutionary Party (PRI). He graduated in Law from the University of Guadalajara and completed a Master's in Public Policies and Management at the Western Institute of Technology and Higher Education (ITESO) (Report Aired in December 2020).

Segundo Moscovici (2015), the constant reproduction of these images and speeches contributes to reinforcing messages and social representations. In this case, it's noted as a strategy to potentially evoke public sentiment regarding the issue of criminality. However, as these messages are disseminated, newspapers begin to convey that these types of crimes are not related to the overall configuration of criminal acts in Puerto Vallarta; they are commissioned and isolated crimes. This contributes to a narrative where such an act stands apart from the local reality, given that they only targeted Aristotle, from behind, after he went alone to the bathroom.

Therefore, this type of situation, such as the murder, is not commonplace in daily life in Puerto Vallarta. From this perspective, the fear that tourists might have and the potential deterrence from visiting Puerto Vallarta doesn't strongly solidify. There isn't an internalization of a representation of the region as unsafe for tourists, especially foreigners.

Regarding Class 3 (Criminal Organizations), most of the content revolves around

notorious criminals and criminal organizations known worldwide, such as news reports from 2016 narrating the kidnapping of El Chapo's son or news about the criminal actions of the Jalisco New Generation Cartel (CJNG).

These reports, besides recounting the crimes, also revisit the historical context of the criminal activities committed by these organizations and the conflicts between them. In the news about El Chapo's son's kidnapping (9 reports from 2016), for instance, it recalls the offenses committed by his father and brothers, as well as revisiting conflicts with other cartels and the police, showing excerpts from news broadcasts aired during the years when the conflicts occurred.

In one of these reports, aired in August 2016, discussing El Chapo's son's kidnapping and the Mexican police investigation lines, the exposure of violence is privileged through frames of police coverage. As a discursive strategy to revive popular memory, the news coverage emphasizes the shootout that occurred in Puerto Vallarta in 1992, highlighting numbers like **'more than a thousand shots were fired inside and outside the Christine nightclub in Puerto Vallarta in less than eight minutes'** (Highlighted by the author). The same report states that in recent years, over 15 impactful shootings have occurred in the region due to conflicts between Mexican cartels. Only after this recollection does the report begin to inform and explain possible reasons for the kidnapping.

These groups, as pointed out by Becker (2002), have a rivalry for power, and the author argues that there are internal and inter-group 'para-social' rules, meaning rules outside the state's regulations. To a large extent, conflicts among criminal organizations arise from the breach of these rules. They are subjected to a general rule (the community rule they belong to), and they all create their own norms for their members, with violations occurring within the groups as well as between them.

Furthermore, it is pertinent to highlight

the contemporary trend of glorifying the major leaders of cartels, such as El Chapo and Pablo Escobar, whose TV series were developed and gained international notoriety, becoming the most watched shows for a certain period of time. This contributes to portraying them as heroic figures endowed with a para-state power in the face of state neglect.

When analyzing the entire corpus through a word cloud, a method where the size of the word is directly related to its frequency, it is noticeable that words like 'detain', 'investigate', 'man', 'police' stand out compared to others (Figure 2).

Fig. 2 – Word cloud of the contents of the news reports²

This happens because, although the reports showcase crime in Puerto Vallarta, their focus is on portraying police action to their viewers, highlighting operations, investigations, and the resolution of crimes. It is inferred that this occurs as an attempt to minimize the negative impacts that such news, even though they differ from the everyday life of the 'common citizen,' might negatively affect the representations of Puerto Vallarta as a good tourist destination, thereby impacting the local economy.

Therefore, it can be said that there is control over the construction of narratives and facts, where the media select 'themes and prioritizes the representations that circulate in the popular imagination', considering 'the interests of those who reproduce them, but also the diffuse feelings of society regarding a

² Source: Developed by the authors using IRAMUTEQ (2021)

certain fact' (Andrade & Doula, p.17-18, 2020).

Therefore, the media gains the power to create and foster a local reality and the various contexts it seeks to represent. In this way, the construction of facts begins to resonate across multiple activities, affecting daily life and influencing the economy, as in the case of Puerto Vallarta's tourism.

5. Final Remarks

The study revealed that, to some extent, the reality of local crimes isn't covered by national media. Criminality is depicted only when it possesses an eccentric character, meaning it has the power to attract public attention by deviating from the ordinary or being related to public figures. It's inferred that this occurs as a strategy to maintain the local economy secure since the perception of insecurity could impact tourism in Puerto Vallarta. Regarding the coverage of reports about drug trafficking and criminal organizations, it's observed that they focus on globally recognized figures for their influence in the criminal world, such as, for example, the 'El Chapo' family.

The media, however, in depicting criminality in Puerto Vallarta, aims to structure a reality that promotes in the public the need to express somewhat generic and diffuse ideas about crime in the region. Even though they frame criminality in their news coverage and allow an anchoring on crime, they do not represent the reality expressed by public safety statistics. Therefore, even though representations of crimes against women are not widely disseminated, according to INEGI, they perceive the region as unsafe. However, considering this is a touristic region and that representations are laden with meanings and a desire to spread them, it can be perceived that denying everyday criminality leads to the absence of a representation of insecurity for those who do not live in the city's daily life, in this case, the tourists.

Based on the results found in this study, it is believed that future works could analyze how the regional media portrays crime in the tourist region of Puerto Vallarta, given that the national media focuses its reports solely on organized crime or eccentric situations that deviate from the local daily routine.

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